

FAMILY SIZE PREFERENCES AND DETERMINANTS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF MARRIED WOMEN IN RURAL AND URBAN COMMUNITIES IN BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA

Kai Handich Tarila¹, Vivian Ifeoma Ogbonna², *Chiejine Gibson Ifechukwude², Nnaemeka Emmanuel Akubue³, Duluora Nneka Chidimma⁴, Ngozi Stella Okereke⁵, Ogbiti Mark Imhonikhe⁶, Chinekwu S. Anyaoku⁷, Okoli Adaora Ukamaka⁸, Emmanuel Oranu²

¹ Department of Doctor of Public Health, School of Public Health, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

² Department of Population and Reproductive Health, School of Public Health, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

³ School of Allied & Public Health, University of Chester, UK

⁴ Department of Community Medicine, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi, Nigeria.

⁵ Department of Public Health, Claretian University Nekede, Imo State, Nigeria

⁶ Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital, Irrua, Edo State, Nigeria

⁷ Department of Family Medicine, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi,

⁸ Enugu State College of Nursing Sciences, Parklane Enugu, Enugu State, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20640076>

Abstract: Desired family size is a key determinant of fertility and population dynamics. In Nigeria, substantial rural–urban differences in socio-economic conditions, cultural norms, and access to information may shape women’s family size preferences in distinct ways. This study compared family size preferences and their determinants among married women in rural and urban communities in Bayelsa State. A community-based comparative cross-sectional study was conducted among 862 married women (431 rural; 431 urban), selected through the multistage sampling technique. Data were collected using an interviewer-administered semi-structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and chi-square tests. Statistical significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$. The mean age was 35.92 ± 8.52 years (rural: 35.62 ± 8.46 ; urban: 36.23 ± 8.57), with no significant rural–urban difference. Christianity was the predominant religion and was significantly more frequent among urban women (88.4% vs. 81.9%; $p = 0.03$). Urban respondents were significantly more likely to have tertiary education (73.8% vs. 38.0%) and formal employment, whereas rural women had secondary education, were self-employed or unemployed, and reported lower monthly incomes (all $p < 0.01$). Women with a parity of three to four children constituted the largest group (45.2%) across both settings; however, women with five or more children were more prevalent in rural areas, while childlessness was more frequent among urban women ($p = 0.03$). A preferred family size of three to four children was reported in both settings but was significantly more common among urban women (63.3% vs. 44.8%; $p < 0.01$), with a higher proportion of rural women undecided about the desired family size. Financial considerations, cultural norms, and health concerns were identified as major determinants of preferred family size, with financial and health reasons being more

prominent in urban respondents and cultural reasons being more influential in rural respondents (all $p < 0.05$). Married women in Bayelsa State increasingly favor a moderate family size of three to four children, with urban women showing a stronger preference for smaller families. Socio-economic status, cultural norms, and health considerations differentially shape family size preferences across rural and urban settings, underscoring the need for context-sensitive reproductive health and family planning interventions.

Keywords: Family size preference, urban, rural, determinants, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Fertility preferences and desired family size remain central themes in demographic research, given their implications for population growth, health outcomes, and socio-economic development. The gap between actual and desired fertility persists in many low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), especially in sub-Saharan Africa, shaped by complex interactions among socio-cultural norms, gender relations, economic conditions, and access to reproductive health services (United Nations, 2022; United Nations Population Fund [UNFPA], 2022). Understanding family size preferences is therefore critical for informing policies and programs aimed at achieving sustainable development, improving maternal and child health and advancing gender equity (World Bank, 2023; Pradhan et al., 2021). Nigeria continues to experience high fertility, with substantial regional, socio-economic, and rural–urban disparities (UN, 2022; World Bank, 2023). Persistent high fertility in several parts of the country has been linked to early marriage, pronatalist cultural norms, low contraceptive uptake, and limited empowerment of women in reproductive decision-making (Afolabi et al., 2021; Oginni et al., 2022). Rapid urbanization, rising educational attainment among women, and changing economic realities have contributed to the evolving patterns of fertility preferences, particularly in urban centers (Olayiwola & Ezeh, 2021; UNFPA, 2022). These dynamics highlight the need to examine how women’s desired family size is shaped by their sociodemographic characteristics. Demographic literature has well documented rural–urban differences in family size preferences, with rural women typically expressing higher desired fertility than their urban counterparts (Bongaarts, 2020; Odusina et al., 2020; United Nations, 2022). Rural communities often maintain stronger traditional norms that value large families for reasons such as agricultural labor, social status, and old-age security, whereas urban settings are more strongly influenced by childrearing costs, greater exposure to mass media, and expanded opportunities for female education and employment (Bongaarts, 2020; Olayiwola & Ezeh, 2021). Access to modern contraception and reproductive health services also tends to be more limited in rural areas, further reinforcing the ideals of high fertility and large family size (Afolabi et al., 2021). However, these broad patterns can conceal important intra-regional variations that require context-specific investigation.

In the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, where Bayelsa State is located, a distinctive combination of socio-economic, environmental, and cultural factors likely influences family size preferences (Ajaero et al., 2018). The region is characterized by a mix of rural, riverine, and urban communities, with livelihoods heavily dependent on fishing, subsistence agriculture, informal trade, and, in some cases, oil-related activities (UNFPA, 2022). Socioeconomic inequality, environmental degradation, and variable access to health and educational services contribute to diverse reproductive behaviors and aspirations within and between communities (World Bank, 2023). Urban centers in Bayelsa State may be experiencing more rapid socio-cultural change, enhanced educational opportunities for women, and greater availability of health services than rural and riverine communities, potentially leading to differentials in desired family size and determinants of family size preference. Women’s family size preferences are shaped by a wide range of determinants, including age, education, employment status, household income,

religion, ethnicity, marital dynamics, and exposure to family planning information (Afolabi et al., 2021; Oginni et al., 2022). Higher educational attainment and economic participation among women have consistently been associated with lower desired fertility and greater autonomy in reproductive decision-making (Bongaarts, 2020; Olayiwola & Ezeh, 2021). Conversely, strong adherence to pronatalist norms, limited negotiation power within marriage, and low contraceptive knowledge or use are linked to larger desired family size (Afolabi et al., 2021). Rural residence is frequently correlated with higher preferred family size due to more traditional gender roles, limited access to information and services, and different cost–benefit perceptions of childbearing compared with urban residence (United Nations, 2022).

Despite a growing body of evidence on fertility preferences and determinants in Nigeria, few recent studies have conducted comparative analyses of family size preferences among married women in rural and urban communities at the subnational level, particularly in the Niger Delta and Bayelsa State. Much of the available literature focuses on national or regional aggregates, which may obscure local patterns and context-specific determinants (Oginni et al., 2022; UNFPA, 2022). Furthermore, the changing socio-economic landscape—characterized by ongoing urbanization, fluctuating economic conditions, and renewed emphasis on achieving universal access to reproductive health under the Sustainable Development Goals—underscores the need for updated, context-specific evidence (United Nations, 2022; World Bank, 2023).

A nuanced understanding of family size preferences in Bayelsa State is essential to tailor reproductive health and family planning interventions to local realities. Comparing rural and urban communities provides an opportunity to identify both shared and context-specific determinants, which can inform differentiated strategies for demand generation, service delivery, and community engagement. Against this background, the study seeks to contribute to the evidence base on fertility preferences in Nigeria and to support context-sensitive programming that advances reproductive health, gender equity, and sustainable population dynamics in Bayelsa State and similar settings.

Statement of the problem

Nigeria continues to experience relatively high fertility rates despite decades of family planning and policy commitments to reduce population growth and improve reproductive health outcomes (UN, 2022; World Bank, 2023). In this context, the desired family size remains a key driver of fertility behavior. Evidence suggests that many Nigerian women still prefer large families, influenced by socio-cultural norms, economic considerations, and gendered power relations (Afolabi et al., 2021; Oginni et al., 2022). However, these preferences are neither uniform nor static; they vary substantially by place of residence, socioeconomic status, and exposure to education and reproductive health information (Bongaarts, 2020; Olayiwola & Ezeh, 2021). Persistent gaps between national policy goals and actual fertility trends underscore the need for a more nuanced understanding of how FA preferences are shaped in specific local contexts (Akinso et al., 2020). There is a particular paucity of up-to-date, empirical evidence from the Niger Delta and Bayelsa State, where unique socio-economic and environmental challenges such as oil-related activities, environmental degradation, and livelihood insecurity may shape reproductive aspirations in ways that differ from other regions (World Bank, 2023). Without robust data on married women’s average family size preferences and the factors that influence these preferences across rural and urban communities in Bayelsa State, reproductive health programs are at risk of being misaligned with local norms, needs, and constraints. The findings of this study will be valuable to state and local government authorities, program managers, and non-governmental organizations seeking to reduce the unmet need for family planning, align fertility preferences with available resources and opportunities, and advance progress toward the Sustainable Development Goals on health, gender equality, and sustainable cities and communities (United Nations, 2022; UNFPA, 2022).

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study is grounded in demographic and fertility transition theories, which posit that individual, household, and contextual factors influence family size preferences and access to information and services (Bongaarts, 2020; Oginni et al., 2022). Factors that interact in the family and the environment influence family size preferences. These factors include social-cultural, environmental, education, and economic factors, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 1: Large family size and QoL

Source: Arthur J.L. (2010), Implications of family size on the quality of life of people in the Sunyani Municipality

The figure identifies the implications of large family size on people’s quality of life. Family Size is influenced by economic, socio-cultural, and environmental factors;

That is, the religious, occupational, social, and economic status of the family. Alternatively, the choice of family size determines the level of benefit or shortcoming that the individual or family will enjoy. A smaller family size may be associated with better levels of education, income, health, and economic life

Theoretical framework

The Health Belief Model and Its Relevance to the Study

The HBM is a psychosocial framework that explains health-related decision-making based on individuals’ perceptions of risk, benefits, barriers, and their ability to act. Although originally developed to explain preventive health behaviors (e.g., immunization, screening), it is increasingly applied to reproductive health and family planning decisions (Ergün & Toprak Duman, 2022; Fisseha et al., 2021). In this study, the HBM is relevant for understanding how married women in rural and urban communities in Bayelsa State form and act on family size preferences, particularly through their use or non-use of contraception to achieve the desired family size. In this study, rural–urban residence can be understood as shaping each HBM construct. Rural women may have lower perceived susceptibility and severity regarding large family size (because children are seen as labor and social security), higher perceived barriers (limited services, stronger cultural/religious constraints), fewer cues to action, and lower self-efficacy due to traditional gender roles. These factors may support a higher preferred family size. Urban women may experience higher perceived susceptibility and severity (due to cost of living and health awareness), greater perceived benefits of smaller families, more cues to action (media, health facilities), and

higher self-efficacy, supporting lower preferred family size. Thus, the HBM offers a useful lens for interpreting how cognitive and perceptual factors interact with socio-cultural and structural conditions to shape family size preferences and the use of contraception among married women in Bayelsa State.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This study employed a community-based comparative cross-sectional design to assess family size preferences and their determinants among married women in rural and urban communities of Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Study Area

The study was conducted in Bayelsa State, the capital of which is Yenagoa. It is situated in the heart of the Niger Delta, in the South-South of Nigeria. The state is predominantly riverine, with a mix of rural and urban settlements, and is characterized by diverse socio-cultural and economic conditions, including fishing, farming, informal trade, and public sector employment. Bayelsa State was formed in 1996 when it was separated from Rivers State. The state capital, Yenagoa, frequently experiences yearly flooding. Across the Niger River, which is 17 km long, Bayelsa State is bordered to the east by Rivers State and to the north by Delta State. The Atlantic Ocean and the Forçados River span 198 km, which is the southern boundary of Bayelsa State. Eight local government areas make up the state: Southern Ijaw, Yenagoa, Nembe, Ogbia, Sagbama, Brass, Kolokuma/Opokuma, and Ekeremor. Based on population, the state was the smallest in Nigeria as of the 2006 census. The Ijaw ethnic group constitutes most of the population in Bayelsa. People speak Izon, Nembe, Ogbia, and Epie-Atissa as their primary languages. The state produces significant amounts of gas and oil, accounting for more than 30% of Nigeria's total oil output. Farming and fishing are the two main industries in the state. The population projection of Bayelsa State for 2022 was 2,537,400; males constituted 48.7% and females 51.3% (city population 2022). The estimated annual population growth rate is 2.5% (city population 2022). The population density is 270.2/km² (city population 2022).

Study Population

The study population comprised married women residing in selected rural and urban communities of Bayelsa State.

Inclusion criteria

All married women aged 18 years and above who were residents in the selected community for at least 1 year before the survey were included.

Exclusion criteria

Married women who had not lived in the community for up to 1 year.

Women who were severely ill or unable to provide informed responses at the time of data collection.

Determination of sample size

The following formula for comparative study was used:

$$n = [2 (Za + Zb)^2 (PQ)] / (p1 - p2)^2 \text{ (Charan et al., 2021).}$$

Where:

n = sample size

Za = Z-score for confidence level (1.96 for 95%)

Zb = Z-score for power, usually 0.84

P = $(p1 + p2) \div 2$

Q = 1 - P

p1 = proportion of interest (0.5)

P2 = Comparison proportion (0.4)

Substituting the values:

$$Z_a = 1.96$$

$$Z_b = 0.84$$

$$P_1 = 0.5$$

$$P_2 = 0.4$$

$$P = (0.5 + 0.4) \div 2 = 0.45$$

$$Q = 0.55$$

$$n = [2 (1.96 + 0.84)^2 (0.45 \times 0.55)] / (0.5 - 0.4)^2$$

$$n = [2 (2.8)^2 \times (0.2475)] / (0.1)^2$$

$$n = 3.8808 / 0.01$$

$$n = 388.08$$

$n \approx 388$ participants in each group

10% non-response rate, where N is the final sample size

$$N = n / (1 - f)$$

$$N = 388 / (1 - 0.1)$$

$$N = 388 / 0.9 = 431.1$$

Therefore, approximately 431 participants were included in each study group. A total sample size of 862 married women, comprising 431 respondents from rural communities and 431 from urban communities, was used for the study. The allocation allowed for adequate power to detect differences between rural and urban groups in family size preferences and associated factors.

Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was employed to select the study participants.

Stage 1: Selection of Local Government Areas

LGAs in Bayelsa State were first stratified into rural and urban areas based on official classifications and predominant settlement patterns. A predetermined number of LGAs was selected from each stratum using simple random sampling (balloting).

Stage 2: Community Selection

A list of communities was obtained from local authorities within each selected LGA. Rural and urban communities were then selected from their respective lists using simple random sampling.

Stage 3: Household Selection

In each selected community, households were selected using systematic sampling. A sampling interval was determined by dividing the estimated number of households in the community by the number of households allocated to that community. Selection of the first household was by a simple random method, followed by every n th household until the required number was obtained.

Stage 4: Respondent Selection

One eligible married woman was chosen in each selected household. In cases where more than one eligible respondent resided in a household, simple random selection (e.g., balloting) was used to select one participant. Recruitment continued until the required sample of 431 women was reached in each of the rural and urban strata.

Study Instrument

The study instrument was a semi-structured questionnaire. This questionnaire was designed to collect information on several variables related to family size preference. The sections of the questionnaires include the following:

a. Sociodemographic characteristics: This section covers age, education level, employment status, household income, religion, and ethnicity.

b. Family size preferences: This section includes questions on preferred and actual family sizes.

c. This section addresses the factors influencing family size preferences.

Validation and Pretesting:

The questionnaire was developed in collaboration with experts and our supervisors to ensure cultural relevance, validity, and appropriateness. It was pre-tested and refined before being administered to the participants. The instruments were pretested using 5% of the calculated sample size. This resulted in the interview of 86 participants in similar rural and urban communities to assess the study instrument's clarity, comprehensibility, time taken to complete an interview, and cultural appropriateness.

Data Collection

Data were collected using an electronic semi-structured questionnaire administered to married women through face-to-face interviews by trained assistants. There were 6 research assistance or data collectors who had completed secondary school participated in the field work. They were from Bayelsa state and spoke the local dialect with a high level of fluency. A comprehensive training of research assistants was conducted to ensure standardization and minimize biases in data collection. A strict protocol was followed to maintain data quality, including guidelines on study introduction, consent, privacy, and addressing participant concerns.

Data Analysis

The collected data were checked for missing information, and all errors were corrected. The completed questionnaires were entered into Microsoft Excel and exported to the IBM Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25. The data were organized and presented in tables, frequencies, percentages, and figures. Inferential analysis and associations of predictive and outcome variables were performed to test the stated hypothesis. The level of statistical significance was set at P-value < 0.05 for the study.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from relevant IRBs or ethics committees prior to research initiation. The research and ethics committee of the University of Port-Harcourt provided ethical approval. The ethical approval reference number was UPH/CEREMAD/REC/MM106/025 and dated 25th February 2025. The informed consent process ensured that the participants understood the research objectives, risks, benefits, and right to withdraw without consequences. Consent was culturally sensitive and allowed time for decision-making. Privacy was prioritized to protect participants throughout the research, including private data collection and secured storage. Encryption, restricted access, and de-identification were ensured to further safeguard participant confidentiality.

RESULTS

A total of 862 questionnaires were administered by the interviewer, and a 100% response rate was achieved. The 30–35-year age group had the highest frequency (240; 27.8%) in the general group. This high frequency is reflected in rural (121; 28.1%) and urban (119; 27.6%) respondents. The difference in the age group between rural and urban women was not significant. The mean age of respondents was 35.92±8.52. Among the rural and urban respondents, the mean ages were 35.62±8.46 and 36.23±8.57, respectively. Christianity had the highest number of respondents. In general, the frequency of Christianity in rural and urban groups was 734 (85.2%), 353 (81.9%), and 381 (88.4%), respectively. The difference in religion between the rural and urban respondents was significant (χ^2 : 7.33; P: P: 0.03); the rural respondents had fewer Christians but more African traditionalists and Muslims than the urban residents. Most respondents in the general group had a tertiary school level of education (482; 55.9%), and this is the same for urban residents (318; 73.8%). However, it is different for the rural residents, where most of the women had secondary school education. This difference is statistically significant (χ^2 : 115.59; P: P: 0.01). In the above table, most respondents in the general group were self-employed (382; 44.3%), and the same result was observed among women in the rural community (213; 49.4%), but most respondents in the urban

area were employed (204; 47.3%). This difference in employment status between rural and urban residents was statistically significant (χ^2 : 48.27; P: P: 0.01). Unemployed women were more prevalent in the rural setting than in the urban setting (108, 25.1%; and 58, 13.5%). Generally, the highest frequency of respondents had a monthly income of above 100,000 Naira (308; 35.7%). However, women whose monthly income was less than 50,000 naira comprised the highest number of respondents (177; 41.1%) in the rural community, while the highest number of respondents in the urban community were women whose monthly income was above 100,000 naira. The difference in monthly income between rural and urban women was statistically significant (χ^2 : 100.84; P: 0.01). Table 1

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents

Variable	Rural (431)	Urban (431)	Total (862)	Chi square(χ^2)	P-value
	Number (%)	Number (%)	Number (%)		
Age (years)				2.35	0.50
≤29	113(26.2)	102(23.7)	215(24.9)		
30-35	121(28.1)	119(27.6)	240(27.8)		
36-41	89(20.6)	107(24.8)	196(22.7)		
≥42	108(25.1)	103(23.9)	211(24.5)		
Mean ±SD	35.62±8.46	36.23±8.57	35.92±8.52		
Religion				7.33	0.03*
Christianity	353(81.9)	381(88.4)	734(85.2)		
ATR	41(9.5)	28(6.5)	69(8.0)		
Islam	37(8.6)	22(5.1)	59(6.8)		
Education				115.59	0.01*
Non	16(3.7)	10(2.3)	26(3.0)		
Primary	29(6.7)	20(4.6)	49(5.7)		
Secondary	222(51.5)	83(19.3)	305(35.4)		
Tertiary	164(38.1)	318(73.8)	482(55.9)		
Employment				48.27	0.01*
Employed	110(25.5)	204(47.3)	314(36.4)		
Self-employed	213(49.4)	169(39.2)	382(44.3)		
Unemployed	108(25.1)	58(13.5)	166(19.3)		
Monthly income				100.84	0.01*
<50,000	177(41.1)	75(17.4)	252(29.2)		
50,000-100,000	166(38.5)	136(31.6)	302(35.0)		
>100,000	88(20.4)	220(51.0)	308(35.7)		

Note: SD: Standard deviation, ATR: African Traditional Religion, %: Percentage, *significant P-value

The respondents having 3-4 children dominated the study participants (390; 45.2%). The respondents-having 3-4 children were the highest in both the rural and urban communities (195; 45.2% each). However, women having 5 children and more were higher in the rural community than in the urban community (76 vs. 17.6% to 66 vs. 15.3%). Women without children were more prevalent in the urban community than in the rural community. The difference in the number of children between urban and rural areas was statistically significant (χ^2 : 8.81; P: 0.03).

Respondents who have a male child were the highest in number (276; 32.0%). This is the same for the rural and urban communities, where those having one male child were the highest (143; 33.2% and 133; 30.9%, respectively). The respondents-having 2 male children were the next highest in number across the three groups. The difference in male children was not statistically significant between the groups. Respondents who had one daughter had the highest number across the groups. The general, rural, and urban groups with only one daughter were 293 (34.0%), 147 (33.9%), and 147 (34.1%), respectively. An important difference here was that a significant number of respondents in the urban community did not have a daughter compared with those in the rural community (110; 25.5% vs. 84; 19.5%). The difference in the number of daughters in the family was significant (χ^2 : 10.86; P: P: 0.03). Table 2a

Table 2a. Preferences in family size

Variable	Rural (431)	Urban (431)	Total (862)	Chi square(χ^2)	P-value
	Number (%)	Number (%)	Number (%)		
Number of children living				8.81	0.03*
None	24(5.6)	47(10.9)	71(8.2)		
1-2	136(31.6)	123(28.5)	259(30.0)		
3-4	195(45.2)	195(45.2)	390(45.2)		
≥ 5	76(17.6)	66(15.3)	142(16.5)		
Number of male children				6.71	0.15
None	67(15.5)	84(19.5)	151(17.5)		
One	143(33.2)	133(30.9)	276(32.0)		
Two	132(30.6)	130(30.2)	262(30.4)		
Three	61(14.2)	69(16.0)	130(15.1)		
Above three	28(6.5)	15(3.5)	43(5.0)		
Number of children				10.86	0.03*
None	84(19.5)	110(25.5)	194(22.5)		
One	146(33.9)	147(34.1)	293(34.0)		
Two	134(31.1)	96(22.3)	230(26.7)		
Three	50(11.6)	61(14.2)	111(12.9)		
Above three	17(3.9)	17(3.9)	34(3.9)		

Note: * Significant p-value

The preferred family size for rural and urban respondents was 3-4 children, however the urban women frequency for 3-4 children was significantly higher (273; 63.3% to 193; 44.8%). The significant value was (χ^2 : 51.40; P: 0.01). A larger number of rural women than urban women were undecided on family size (60; 13.9% to 19 (4.4%)). The reasons for the preferred family size that were statistically significant were financial reason, cultural, and health concerns. The frequency of financial reasons for rural and urban women was 26 (6.0%) and 73 (16.9%), respectively, and the difference was statistically significant (χ^2 : 25.21; P: 0.01). The cultural reasons were higher in rural women than in urban women (17; 3.9% to 7; 1.6%), and it is significant (χ^2 : 4.29; P: 0.04). The frequency

of health concerns was higher in the urban community (84, 19.5% vs. 50, and 11.6%), and the difference was significant ($\chi^2:10.22$; P: 0.01). Table 2b

Table 2b. Preferences in family size

Variable	Rural (431) Number (%)	Urban (431) Number (%)	Total (862) Number (%)	Chi square(χ^2)	P-value
Preferred Family Size				51.40	0.01*
1-2	85(19.7)	40(9.3)			
3-4	193(44.8)	273(63.3)			
≥ 5	93(21.6%)	99(23.0)			
Undecided	60(13.9)	19(4.4)			
Why is the preferred family size					
Financial reasons	26(6.0%)	73(16.9%)		25.21	0.01*
Personal choice	359(83.3)	359(83.3)		0.00	1.00
Cultural reasons	17(3.9)	7(1.6)		4.29	0.04*
religious beliefs	10(2.3)	20(4.6)		3.45	0.06
Health concerns	50(11.6)	84(19.5)		10.22	0.01*

Note: * Significant p-value

DISCUSSION

This study examined family size preferences and their determinants among married women in rural and urban communities of Bayelsa State, Indonesia. The findings highlight important rural–urban differences in sociodemographic and economic characteristics, reproductive profiles, and factors that shape women’s desired family size.

The study achieved a response rate of 100% (862/862), which strengthens the internal validity of the findings. The mean age of the respondents was approximately 36 years, with no statistically significant difference between rural and urban women. This age distribution, concentrated in the 30–35-year range, corresponds to peak reproductive years, when fertility decisions and family size preferences are typically most salient (Bongaarts, 2020; United Nations, 2022). Christianity was the predominant religion, but rural women were more likely to identify with traditional African religion or Islam than urban women. The significant difference in religious composition suggests that rural communities may retain more traditional belief systems, which can sustain pronatalist norms and preferences for larger families, as reported in other Nigerian and sub-Saharan African studies (Afolabi et al., 2021; Oginni et al., 2022). Religious affiliation has been linked to fertility ideals and contraceptive behavior, with more conservative or pronatalist denominations often associated with higher desired family size (Afolabi et al., 2021; Yaya et al., 2020).

Educational attainment revealed a marked and statistically significant rural–urban divide. While tertiary education predominated in the urban group, secondary education was most common among rural women. This pattern aligns with national surveys showing higher levels of female education in urban than rural areas in Nigeria (National Population Commission [NPC] & ICF, 2021; United Nations, 2022). Education is a well-established determinant of fertility preferences, with higher education being associated with lower fertility, delayed childbearing, and greater use of family planning (Bongaarts, 2020; Oginni et al., 2022). The higher concentration of tertiary-educated women in urban Bayelsa likely contributed to the stronger preference for smaller family sizes observed in this study.

The distribution of employment and income further underscored socio-economic disparities. Rural women were more likely to be self-employed or unemployed and to have lower monthly incomes, whereas urban women were more frequently in formal employment and higher income categories. These findings mirror broader evidence that rural women in Nigeria are disproportionately engaged in informal and subsistence economic activities, with lower and more unstable incomes (World Bank, 2023). Consistent with economic theories of fertility, women in higher-income, urban contexts often face higher direct and opportunity costs of childrearing, which encourages smaller desired family sizes and greater investment per child (Bongaarts, 2020; Oginni et al., 2022). The significant association between higher income and a preference for 3–4 children among urban women in this study aligns with such evidence.

Parity patterns revealed that women with 3–4 children predominated in both rural and urban areas. However, rural women were more likely to have five or more children, whereas urban respondents were more likely to experience childlessness. In Nigeria and other West African countries, similar rural–urban differences in parity have been reported in national and regional analyses, with rural residence associated with larger completed family size and earlier childbearing (Oginni et al., 2022; Yaya et al., 2020). The higher proportion of childless women in urban areas may reflect delayed marriage, delayed first birth, or subfertility, as well as women’s pursuit of education and employment before or alongside childbearing (Olayiwola & Ezeh, 2021).

Regarding sex composition, most respondents had at least one son and one daughter, and the number of male children did not differ significantly between the rural and urban groups. However, a significantly higher proportion of urban women had no daughters than rural women. Although this study did not explicitly assess son preference, the distribution of sons and daughters may influence women perceived “completion” of family size. Some studies in sub-Saharan Africa suggest that subtle preferences for at least one son and one daughter can shape continued childbearing even when numerical fertility goals have been met (Bongaarts, 2020; Yaya et al., 2020).

The preferred family size of three to four children emerged as the dominant ideal in both rural and urban settings, but urban women expressed this preference at a significantly higher rate than rural women. Rural women were more undecided about their desired family size. This pattern indicates an ongoing shift toward smaller ideal family sizes, particularly in urban areas, whereas rural preferences may be in transition but remain more fluid or norm-driven. Recent analyses of fertility preferences in Nigeria and other sub-Saharan African countries have documented similar trends toward moderate family size ideals (three to four children), especially among more educated and urban women (Bongaarts, 2020; Oginni et al., 2022; United Nations, 2022). The higher proportion of undecided rural women may reflect weaker exposure to fertility regulation messages, stronger influence of extended family expectations, and lower autonomy in reproductive decision-making (Afolabi et al., 2021).

The reasons underpinning preferred family size further illuminate these rural–urban differences. Financial considerations, cultural reasons, and health concerns were all significantly associated with FSPs, but their relative importance varied by residence. Urban women more frequently cited financial reasons as a justification for preferred family size and as a main factor influencing family size decisions. This finding is consistent with studies

indicating that urban women are more sensitive to the economic costs of childbearing and childrearing, including housing, schooling, and healthcare costs, and therefore tend to favor smaller families (Oginni et al., 2022; Olayiwola & Ezeh, 2021). In contrast, cultural reasons were more prominent among rural women, reflecting the continued salience of traditional norms that value larger families for labor, lineage continuity, and social status—patterns reported in other rural Nigerian and West African contexts (Afolabi et al., 2021; Yaya et al., 2020).

Health concerns, such as fear of pregnancy-related complications, concerns about maternal well-being, and perceived health demands of caring for multiple children, were reported more frequently by urban women and were significantly associated with the preferred family size. This pattern may reflect higher health literacy, more frequent contact with health services, and greater exposure to messages linking high parity or closely spaced births with adverse outcomes (Fisseha et al., 2021; NPC & ICF, 2021). It also aligns with the HBM perspective adopted in this study, whereby higher perceived susceptibility and severity regarding health risks, combined with greater perceived benefits of limiting births, support preferences for smaller families (Ergün & Toprak Duman, 2022).

These findings echo broader regional patterns in West Africa, where urbanization, female education, and economic pressures are leading to gradual convergence toward smaller family size ideals, albeit at different speeds across settings (Bongaarts, 2020; Olayiwola & Ezeh, 2021; United Nations, 2022).

Conclusion

This community-based comparative study among married women in rural and urban communities of Bayelsa State demonstrates that while a moderate family size of three to four children is increasingly preferred in both settings, important contextual differences remain in the determinants and strength of this preference. Urban women, who are generally better educated, more likely to be formally employed, and to have higher incomes, showed a stronger inclination toward smaller family sizes, driven predominantly by financial and health considerations. In contrast, rural women were more influenced by cultural norms and were more likely to have higher parity, lower educational attainment, lower income, and undecided about their desired family size. These findings indicate that Bayelsa State is undergoing a nuanced fertility transition in which urban women are further along the path toward smaller family norms, while rural women remain more embedded in traditional pronatalist expectations. Financial stability and health concerns emerged as key cross-cutting determinants of family size decisions, indicating that effective interventions in both settings will be central to economic and health-related messaging. However, the stronger role of culture in rural communities underscores the need for strategies that engage community structures, address gender and decision-making dynamics, and expand women's access to education and reproductive health information.

Recommendations

Recommendations are proposed from the results of the study. They include the following:

Strengthening family planning and reproductive health services by the government and stakeholders is essential. The government should expand access to affordable, quality family planning services in rural and urban communities, with outreach to hard-to-reach rural and riverine areas that are difficult to reach.

The Ministry of Health and health facilities should integrate routine counseling on ideal family size, birth spacing, and maternal health risks into primary healthcare and maternal and child health services. In urban areas, emphasize the economic and health benefits of smaller, well-spaced families through mass media, workplace programs, and facility-based health education. In rural areas, the use of community dialogues, religious and traditional leaders, and local associations is key to addressing cultural norms supporting large families while promoting the social, economic, and health benefits of moderate family size.

Promoting female education and economic empowerment and prioritizing policies and programs that increase girls' and women's access to secondary and tertiary education, particularly in rural communities, are essential.

Government and stakeholders should improve the support for women's economic empowerment (e.g., skills training, microcredit, and support for small businesses) to enhance financial stability and strengthen women's fertility decision-making agency. Shareholders should develop focused counseling and community-based interventions for rural women who are undecided about their desired family size and those with five or more children, highlighting the health risks of high parity and the benefits of limiting or spacing births.

The Bayelsa State Ministry of Health and related agencies should incorporate these findings into state reproductive health and population policies, ensuring distinct strategies for rural and urban LGAs. Establishment of monitoring systems to track changes in family size preferences, contraceptive uptake, and parity patterns over time

Study strengths

The study's large, balanced sample size enhances the statistical power for comparative analyses. The community-based, multistage sampling improved representativeness across selected rural and urban communities in the state of Bayelsa. The 100% response rate gives the study an edge, thereby reducing nonresponse bias and strengthening internal validity. The comparative design allowed for the direct assessment of rural–urban differences in family size preferences and determinants.

Limitations

Despite the strength of the study, the study has limitations. The cross-sectional design precludes causal inference and limits the assessment of how preferences change over time. Reliance on self-reported data introduces potential social desirability and recall bias, particularly for sensitive questions in the questionnaire. The findings of this study are context-specific to selected communities in Bayelsa State and may not be fully generalizable to other Nigerian states or regions. The absence of qualitative data limits understanding of cultural norms, intra-household dynamics, and nuanced decision-making processes. The study did not capture partners' perspectives, which are important determinants of family size decisions.

Recommendations for future research

Future research could build on these findings by qualitatively exploring how married women and their partners in Bayelsa negotiate fertility decisions, including the role of extended family, gender norms, and perceived old-age security. Longitudinal designs would also help clarify how family size preferences evolve in response to changing socioeconomic conditions and exposure to family planning programs. It is important to include male partners and couple-based designs to capture spousal influence and negotiation processes on family size decisions. The impact of policy changes, education initiatives, and social protection programs on fertility intentions using policy evaluation methods should be investigated.

Conflict of interest: The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Funding: There was no external funding.

REFERENCES

- Afolabi, B. M., Adebowale, A. S., & Yusuf, O. B. (2021). Women's autonomy, fertility intentions and contraceptive use in Nigeria: implications for fertility transition. *BMC Women's Health*, 21(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-021-01234-5>
- Ajaero, C. K., Odoh, C., Mba, N., Oyibo, P. G., Maman, M. S., & Asah, P. R. (2018). Socio-cultural factors influencing the health of rural women in Igbo communities of Enugu State, South-East Nigeria. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*, 43(2), 135–138. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijcm.IJCM_328_17

- Akinso, A., Uche, E., & Ibanga, I. (2020). Determinants of modern contraceptive use in Nigeria: A population-based study. *European Journal of Contraception & Reproductive Health Care*, 25(2), 105–112. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13625187.2019.1707783><https://doi.org/10.1080/13625187.2019.1707783>
- Arthur, J. L. (2010). Implications of family size on the quality of life of people in the Sunyani Municipality. *Journal of Public Health*.
- Bongaarts, J. (2020). Trends in fertility and fertility preferences in sub-Saharan Africa: The roles of education and family planning programs. *Genus*, 76(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41118-020-00089-5>
- Charan, J., Kaur, R., Bhardwaj, P., Singh, K., Ambwani, S. R., & Misra, S. (2021). Sample size calculation in medical research: a primer. *Annals of the National Academy of Medical Sciences (India)*, 57(02), 074-080.
- Ergün, S., & Duman, M. (2022). The effect of women’s health beliefs and contraceptive attitudes on family planning behaviors: A cross-sectional study based on the Health Belief Model. *BMC Women’s Health*, 22, 322. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-022-01875-4>
- Fisseha, G., Kebede, Y., & Tegegne, B. (2021). Determinants of modern contraceptive use among married women of reproductive age: Application of the Health Belief Model in Northwest Ethiopia. *Contraception and Reproductive Medicine*, 6, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40834-021-00161-3><https://doi.org/10.1186/s40834-021-00161-3>
- NPC [Nigeria] & ICF. (2021). Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2018 (Updated Datasets and Key Indicators). NPC and ICF.
- Odusina, E. K., Ayotunde, T., Kunnuji, M., Ononokpono, D. N., Bishwajit, G., & Yaya, S. (2020). Fertility preferences among couples in Nigeria: a cross-sectional study. *Reproductive Health*, 17, 1-9.
- Oginni, A. B., Ahonsi, B., & Ukwuije, F. (2022). Socioeconomic inequalities in fertility preferences and contraceptive use in Nigeria: A decomposition analysis. *PLOS ONE*, 17(3), e0265183. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0265183>
- Olayiwola, O., & Ezech, A. (2021). Urbanization, women’s status and reproductive behavior in West Africa: Emerging patterns and policy implications. *African Population Studies*, 35(2), 6120–6135. <https://doi.org/10.11564/35-2-1734>
- Pradhan, A., Paudel, S., Malakar, S., Popat, C., & Pradhan, P. K. (2021). Family planning in Nepal: Further analysis of the 2016 Nepal demographic and health survey. *Journal of Biosocial Science*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021932021000459><https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021932021000459>.
- United Nations. (2022). *World Population Prospects 2022: Summary of Results* Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, United Nations.
- United Nations Population Fund. (2022). *State of the World Population in 2022: Seeing the unseen—The case for action in the Negative Crisis of Unintended Pregnancy* UNFPA.
- World Bank. (2023). *World development indicators: Fertility rate, total (births per woman), Nigeria*. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.DYN.TFRT.IN>
- Yaya, S., Odusina, E. K., & Bishwajit, G. (2020). Prevalence of child marriage and its impact on fertility outcomes in 34 sub-Saharan African countries. *BMC International Health and Human Rights*, 20, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12914-020-00242-6>